

Polyaniline/Phenol-Divinylbenzene Resin for CFRP Composite with Enhanced Electrical and Mechanical Properties

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Background and introduction

Current solution for LSP :

Metal foil , metal mesh and metallic coating on CF

Advantage:
High electrical conductivity;
high thermal conductivity;
Drawback:
High cost;
Corrosion;
Extra weight ;

Promising solution for LSP on CFRP

Intrinsically Conductive Polymers (ICPs)

- Easily synthesis
- Low cost
- Easy availability
- Tunable conductivity
- Environmental friendly

Doping and cationic polymerization of DBSA with DVB polymers to form a cross-linked network.

Before and after simulated lightning strike

Manufacturing process

The plausible curing mechanism of phenol-DVB in the presence of protonic acid.

De-doping phenomenon of PANI/DBSA/DVB(PDD) system

- De-doping phenomenon caused by the present of DVB
- PANI(ES)/DBSA $\xrightleftharpoons{\text{reversible}}$ PANI(EB) + DBSA(free)
- DBSA(free) + DVB $\xrightarrow{\text{Irreversible}}$ Start of the cationic polymerization
- Low mechanical property & low efficiency of PANI

Result and Conclusion

Conclusion

- Resin modified with G65 achieves 260% and 32% enhancement in conductivity and fracture modulus, respectively.
- Resin modified with M8005 achieves 220% and 12% enhancement in conductivity and fracture modulus, respectively.
- M8005 ones has better property in viscosity and room temperature stability compared to G65.
- Phenol-modified resin reduces the de-doping phenomenon, which leads to a better applicability in CFRP and LSP area.

Reference

- V. Kumar, T. Yokozeki, T. Goto, and T. Takahashi, "Mechanical and electrical properties of PANI-based conductive thermosetting composites," *J. Reinf. Plast. Compos.*, vol. 34, no. 16, pp. 1298–1305, 2015.
- V. Kumar *et al.*, "Cationic scavenging by polyaniline: Boon or bane from synthesis point of view of its nanocomposites," *Polymer (Guildf)*, vol. 149, pp. 169–177, 201.
- T. Yokozeki *et al.*, "Development and characterization of CFRP using a polyaniline-based conductive thermoset matrix," *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 117, pp. 277–281, 2015.
- V. Kumar, Y. Zhou, G. Shambharkar, V. Kunc, and T. Yokozeki, "Reduced de-doping and enhanced electrical conductivity of polyaniline filled phenol-divinylbenzene composite for potential lightning strike protection application," *Synth. Met.*, vol. 249, 2019.